

SWForum.eu

European forum of the software research community

Deliverable D2.7

Project Radar Landscape Analysis V2

Editor (s):	Rohan Agrawal & Prof. David Wallom
Responsible Partner:	University of Oxford
Status-Version:	Final – V2.0
Date:	July 3, 2023
Distribution level (CO, PU):	PU

Project Number:	GA 957044
Project Title:	SWForum.eu

Title of Deliverable:	Project Radar Landscape Analysis V2
Due Date of Delivery to the EC	30.06.2023

Workpackage responsible for the Deliverable:	WP2 - Cross-fertilization and mapping
Editor(s):	Rohan Agrawal and Prof. David Wallom, UOXF
Contributor(s):	-
Reviewer(s):	Elisabetta di Nitto
Approved by:	All partners
Recommended/mandatory readers:	WP2 & WP3

Abstract:	D2.7 will take stock of the software projects funded in relevant EU funding streams and produce in-depth analyses of the resulting data. For the projects selected, the mini sites will be developed. This is the result of tasks T2.2 and T2.3.
Keyword List:	Technology Radar, Taxonomy, visualization
Licensing information:	This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 Unported (CC BY-SA 3.0) http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/
Disclaimer	This document reflects only the author's views and neither Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein

Document Description

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
V0	21/06/2023	First draft version	UOXF
V1	28/06/2023	Reviewed	POLIMI
V2	03/07/2023	Final version	UOXF

DRAFT

Table of Contents

Contents

Table of Contents	4
List of Figures	5
List of Tables.....	5
Terms and abbreviations.....	6
Executive Summary	7
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Document Structure	9
2 Methodology.....	11
2.1 Technology Radar Rings.....	11
2.1.1 Underlying concepts.....	11
2.1.2 Project Maturity: The rings of the radar.....	12
2.1.3 Open-Source Projects.....	14
2.2 Radar Sectors	14
2.2.1 Tools & Techniques	14
2.2.2 Platforms	14
2.2.3 Languages & Frameworks	14
2.3 The ACM Computing Classification System	14
3 The Analyzed Projects	18
4 The June 2023 Technology Radar.....	19
4.1 Results by Sector.....	19
4.1.1 Tools & Techniques	19
4.1.2 Tools & Techniques and Languages & Frameworks.....	20
4.1.3 Platforms and Tools & Techniques.....	21
4.1.4 Languages & Frameworks	22
4.1.5 Languages & Frameworks and Tools & Techniques.....	23
4.1.6 Tools & Techniques and Platforms.....	24
4.1.7 Platforms	25
4.1.8 Platforms and Languages & Frameworks.....	26
4.1.9 Languages & Frameworks and Platforms.....	27
4.2 Segments Overview	27
5 Conclusions	29
6 References.....	30
Appendix: EC-funded Projects reference	31

List of Figures

FIGURE 1. SWFORUM TECHNOLOGY RADAR VISUALIZATION	<u>75</u>
FIGURE 2. HOW WP2 TASKS FEED INTO EACH OTHER AND, ULTIMATELY, INTO WP4’S MARKETPLACE.....	<u>97</u>
FIGURE 3. MATURITY PROGRESSION OF PROJECTS	<u>ERROR! BOOKMARK NOT DEFINED.9</u>
FIGURE 4. ATTENTION LEVEL REQUIRED FOR SOFTWARE PROJECT MATURITY LEVELS.....	<u>ERROR! BOOKMARK NOT DEFINED.9</u>
FIGURE 5. MECHANICS OF THE TECHNOLOGY RADAR.....	<u>ERROR! BOOKMARK NOT DEFINED.10</u>
FIGURE 6. “TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES” RADAR SEGMENT.....	<u>1913</u>
FIGURE 7. “TOOLS & TECHNIQUES AND LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS” RADAR SEGMENT.....	<u>2014</u>
FIGURE 8. “PLATFORMS AND TOOLS & TECHNIQUES” RADAR SEGMENT	<u>2115</u>
FIGURE 9. “LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS” RADAR SEGMENT	<u>2216</u>
FIGURE 10. “LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS AND TOOLS & TECHNIQUES” RADAR SEGMENT.....	<u>2317</u>
FIGURE 11. “TOOLS & TECHNIQUES AND PLATFORMS” RADAR SEGMENT	<u>2418</u>
FIGURE 12. “PLATFORMS” RADAR SEGMENT	<u>2519</u>
FIGURE 13. “PLATFORMS AND LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS” RADAR SEGMENT	<u>2620</u>
FIGURE 14. “LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS AND PLATFORMS” RADAR SEGMENT	<u>2721</u>
FIGURE 15. MARCH 2022 SWFORUM TECHNOLOGY RADAR, SHOWING 51 ANALYZED PROJECTS DISTRIBUTED RADIALLY INTO BANDS DEPENDING ON THEIR MATURITY LEVEL.	<u>2822</u>

List of Tables

TABLE 1. “TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES” OVERVIEW.....	<u>1914</u>
TABLE 2. “TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES” PROJECTS DETAILS	<u>1914</u>
TABLE 3. “TOOLS & TECHNIQUES AND LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS” OVERVIEW	<u>2015</u>
TABLE 4. “TOOLS & TECHNIQUES AND LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS” PROJECTS DETAILS.....	<u>2015</u>
TABLE 5. “PLATFORMS AND TOOLS & TECHNIQUES” OVERVIEW	<u>2116</u>
TABLE 6. “PLATFORMS AND TOOLS & TECHNIQUES” PROJECTS DETAILS	<u>2116</u>
TABLE 7. “LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS” OVERVIEW	<u>2217</u>
TABLE 8. “LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS” PROJECTS DETAILS	<u>2217</u>
TABLE 9. “LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS AND TOOLS & TECHNIQUES” OVERVIEW	<u>2317</u>
TABLE 10. “LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS AND TOOLS & TECHNIQUES” PROJECTS DETAILS.....	<u>2318</u>
TABLE 11. “TOOLS & TECHNIQUES AND PLATFORMS” OVERVIEW	<u>2418</u>
TABLE 12. “TOOLS & TECHNIQUES AND PLATFORMS” PROJECTS DETAILS	<u>2519</u>
TABLE 13. “PLATFORMS” OVERVIEW.....	<u>2519</u>
TABLE 14. “PLATFORMS” PROJECTS DETAILS.....	<u>2520</u>
TABLE 15. “PLATFORMS AND LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS” OVERVIEW	<u>2620</u>
TABLE 16. “PLATFORMS AND LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS” PROJECTS DETAILS	<u>2621</u>
TABLE 17. “LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS AND PLATFORMS” OVERVIEW	<u>2721</u>
TABLE 18. “LANGUAGES & FRAMEWORKS AND PLATFORMS” PROJECTS DETAILS	<u>2722</u>
TABLE 19. “MARCH 2022 SWFORUM TECHNOLOGY RADAR” OVERVIEW	<u>2722</u>
TABLE 20. LIST OF PROJECTS FUNDED BY EC UNDER THE BROAD CATEGORIES OF SWFORUM.EU	<u>3125</u>

Terms and abbreviations

Blip	A visual placeholder for a specific EU funded project in scope for the SW Radar.
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
Radar	Used in conjunction with CW, SWF, or TW to denote the respective radar visualisation. For example, “SWF Radar” refers to the SWForum.eu Project Radar.
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community
WP	Work Package
SDLC	Software Development Life Cycle
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
MRL	Market Readiness Level
MTRL	Market and Technology Readiness Level

Executive Summary

The SWForum.eu project is a CSA aiming to support a large number of software related projects funded by the European Commission in the H2020 programme. As such it is important that we consider what these projects have created as outputs and where they have gone in terms of exploitation, and hopefully impact, either by the projects themselves or by others who may reuse their outputs.

Utilising the “Technology Radar” methodology developed by ThoughtWorks, the SWForum.eu project used the SWForum taxonomy and a schema that describes guidance on whether a user should invest themselves in the outputs of a project, to produce the radar visualisation as below.

Figure 1. SWForum Technology Radar visualization

The radar is a live product with the visualisation created specific to the state of the landscape at the point it is viewed. In this report, we present the snapshots from previous versions to the current version to track and analyze progress that the projects have made.

The current version shows that several projects have completed their lifecycle and are in the Hold stage where they finished their lifecycle less than 12 months ago, while plenty of projects in the Adopt stage are about to finish their lifecycle within the next 6 months. Most of the

projects worked on implementing new Tools & Techniques, either as a primary focus or secondary, to aid the software development process. We also added a new ring to incorporate Open-Source projects in each segment of the radar to allow for better comparison with successful Open-source projects.

In this report, we first describe the assessment methodology used to understand the current status of the projects. We then describe the different visual clues that are used within this instance of the radar that was introduced previously in deliverable D2.4 Project Radar Taxonomies [1]. For this second edition of D2.7 [2], we present all the projects that have been assessed within the radar, which is followed by the radar presentation itself.

DRAFT

1 Introduction

Many substantial investments have been made by both national governments and the European Commission to support co-ordinated programmes of research and innovation projects within the broad domain of software technologies, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity. Since some of these programmes have now completed and as the European Commission has transitioned from Framework 7 to Horizon 2020, it is important that we are able to evaluate the impact that these programmes have had, and more specifically, how ready the outputs are for utilisation by persons from outside the developing community. As such, in all three of the domains in which SWForum.eu is targeting it is essential that we are able to consider and present to stakeholders in these enterprises (potential users of the technologies, processes and policies developed) the outputs from the projects alongside a systematic method of the evaluation of the outputs, with simple commentary on ease of use of these outputs both generally and more importantly, outside of the team that originally developed them, as explained in Figure 2.

The method chosen by SWForum.eu to present the evaluations of the project outputs has been determined to be a type of technology radar, as pioneered by ThoughtWorks [3]. This methodology allows not only the subdivision of the items classified to be segmented depending on specific criteria, but also their radial distance from the centre allows a second classification to be presented simultaneously.

Figure 2. How WP2 tasks feed into each other and, ultimately, into WP4's marketplace

1.1 Document Structure

In Section 2, we describe in detail the methodology used to design the radar – its 3 sectors, the placement of the rings for each sector, and the type of projects included. This section is repeated from earlier editions to ensure that the document is able to stand alone.

In section 3, we showcase the calls from which all projects come from as well as the type of projects incorporated in the radar.

In Section 4, we display all the projects present in the radar in June 2023 and analyze them based on their sector and ring placement. The projects are colored according to their latest MTRL scores we received from each project. The projects with a black border do not have an MTRL score associated with them.

The document concludes with a discussion about the overall impact of the radar and the a discussion of the visualizations of the state of the landscape it provided us. It also identifies the impact of the findings in the broader scope of the project and on the promotion of projects through the SWForum.eu Forum.

DRAFT

2 Methodology

The SWForum Technology Radar is divided into three radial sections or sectors that allows us to place projects in categories based on their project goals and the broad domains of software technologies, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity. The radar also 5 different rings where each project is placed automatically into based on its lifecycle and the stage it's currently in.

The Technology Radar uses the ACM Computing Classification System taxonomy to further classify projects in descriptive categories and determine the relationship between the project and its position within each sector of the radar.

The Technology Radar as a tool requires a descriptive taxonomy of generalized areas within a specific domain that allows the radial segments to be created. Within these segments a schema describing the relationship between the object and its position within the domain sector and the distance from the centre for the visualisation that is used.

In the following sections both are described, starting with the taxonomy of domains and then the actual schema and application of the Technology Radar to the cybersecurity domain.

2.1 Technology Radar Rings

Assessing software development projects according to maturity allows the reader to make an informed decision as to where and when the project in question should be closer examined, or not examined at all.

This section describes this Technology Radar's rings and the state of maturity they capture for every project included in section 4.

2.1.1 Underlying concepts

As any visualisation technique, this Technology Radar relies on applying several design principles to the data to provide an intuitive reader experience. Combined with an easy-to-understand way of charging values with expressive yet generic semantics, the results allow for swift conveying on large amounts of information.

2.1.1.1 Software Development Lifecycle as a project maturity metaphor

The Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) is a well-known concept capturing the life cycle of any software project, from idea to 'sunsetting', i.e., the discontinuation or retiring a solution, a service, a library, basically any piece of software. The SDLC is comparable to many different concepts; for example, the progression through the SDLC is closely resembling the ascension through the Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) that are ubiquitous in the technology and engineering sectors. With the exception that TRLs do not capture the concept of sunsetting a piece of software.

Therefore, mapping the Technology Radar's *rings*, or states to the SDLC, software, or knowledge in this deliverable's context, would undergo the sequence of assessment shown in Figure 3:

Assess → Trial → Adopt → Hold

Figure 3. Maturity progression of projects

The semantics of these terms are described in section [Error! Reference source not found.2.1.2](#).

2.1.1.2 Proximity to the radar's centre reflects readiness for adoption

A straight mapping of the project maturity on the rings of the radar would be counter-intuitive to the visual message of the radar where the very centre of the radar requires the most attention, the outermost ring the least attention. By contrast, the level of attention to the software maturity levels peaks with “Adopt”, dropping to lower levels at either side of it – not dissimilar to the bell curve as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Attention level required for software project maturity levels

Consequently, projects will progress through the radar not in a linear succession from outermost rings towards the centre. Instead, they will “enter” the radar in the middle, gravitate to the centre (the bull’s eye), then jump to the outermost rings for gradually dropping out of scope of the radar altogether:

Figure 5. Mechanics of the technology radar

2.1.2 Project Maturity: The rings of the radar

The rather generic terms that qualify the rings of the radar need to be further contextualised towards the overall purpose of the radar. In *this* instalment of the Technology Radar report, we will quickly review the focus of the radar, how it works, and what insight it may deliver.

This Technology Radar focuses on project maturity based on its contractual timeline, relative to the point in time the report was generated. It assumes that projects generally progress satisfactorily towards their goals and outcomes – it relies on this being ensured by the funding programme’s own checks and balances. In the case of EU H2020, these are the regular project reviews, and the selection of expert reviewers for the project by the Commission.

The description of each ring of the radar is followed by a general recommendation for projects based on their current lifecycle.

2.1.2.1 Assess

Technical criterion: The project is running and has more than 24 months until project end. Moreover, it has still a considerable amount of time to further mature its results and outputs. Yet, it needs to think about how it will play out the final stretch of project lifetime.

Recommendation: Study the project's high-level description and designated outputs and compare with your own strategy and needs. If there is a match, put the project on a personal/specific short-list for further check-up later.

2.1.2.2 Trial

Technical criterion: The project is running and has less than 24 months but more than 12 months until project end. Moreover, the project has still a considerable amount of time to further mature its results and outputs. Yet, it needs to think about how it will play out the final stretch of project lifetime.

Recommendation: Study the project's high-level description and designated outputs and compare with your own strategy and needs. If there is a match, put the project on a personal/specific short-list for further check-up later.

2.1.2.3 Adopt

Technical criterion: The project is running and has less than 12 months to go but has not reached project end. The project is now seriously busy finalising its planned outputs. That might be a piece of software, an innovative algorithm, or a study whose results may impact your own work. Some of the planned work might have been dropped in order to reach the stated goal for more important outputs.

Recommendation: Check back regularly with the project (either actively or passively) to see how the output you are interested in is progressing. Refine your shortlist based on the results of that exercise; expect your shortlist getting smaller unless there are new projects in the pipeline that stock it up again. For those you consider specifically mature, you should consider first practical trials of integrating the output into your portfolio – not to accomplish it straight away, but to anticipate the level of “integration pain” you may experience later. Click on the project and contact then directly through their mini site on the SWForum hub¹.

2.1.2.4 Hold

Technical criterion: The project finished less than 12 months ago.

If you haven't already decided to integrate the project's outputs into your own business, or more neutrally, operations at large, projects in this stage may still have value to you, but you need to understand the how then the published outputs have fared until now and may fare in the future.

¹ <https://www.swforum.eu/project-hub>

Project results in the IT sector, and especially in the currently very dynamic cybersecurity domain age very quickly, as competition is fierce, and many outputs are superseded by technical innovation, or other projects simply having been faster or more efficient in their execution.

Recommendation: For projects that stayed on your shortlist unto this stage, this is the time to start serious integration trials with stable versions of the output. In the case of study results, or non-IT related outputs, the expected integration pain may affect your overall business strategy and cause changes in operations and processes, rather than technical integration challenges that present themselves with IT integrations.

2.1.2.5 Not Displayed in the Radar

Technical criterion: The project ended more than 12 months.

These projects, though present in the SWForum.eu hub, are no longer displayed in the Technical radar.

2.1.3 Open-Source Projects

Following feedback and input from European Commission reviewers, a fifth ring was added to the radar containing several Open-source projects. These open-source projects are classified into their respective sectors based on their most prominent functionality and usability.

By adding such projects to the outermost ring – marked by a dark grey background – the users can now obtain a higher understanding about the potential outcomes the H2020 projects might produce based on existing successful projects in those domains.

2.2 Radar Sectors

Within the SWForum Technology Radar, there are three sectors as described by the three categories of the SWForum taxonomy of R&I in software technologies, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity. These are summarized below for completeness of this deliverable.

2.2.1 Tools & Techniques

Tools can be components, such as databases, software development tools, such as versions control systems; or more generic categories of tools, such as the notion of polyglot persistence. Techniques include elements of a software development process, such as experience design; and ways of structuring software, such as microservices.

2.2.2 Platforms

Things that we build software on top of such as mobile technologies like Android, virtual platforms like the JVM, or generic kinds of platforms like hybrid clouds.

2.2.3 Languages & Frameworks

This can be any kind of new programming language and/or a language framework.

2.3 The ACM Computing Classification System

We use ACM's CCS Taxonomy to further classify projects into different domains as well as allow users to filter the projects on the radar through this. The taxonomies and their sub-domains are given below:

 Computing Systems and Organization

- Real-time systems
- Architectures
- Embedded and Cyber-Physical Systems
- Dependable and Fault Tolerant Systems and Networks

Software and its Engineering

- Software Organization and Properties
- Software Notations and Tools
- Software Creation and Management

Theory of Computation

- Models of Computation
- Formal Languages and Automata Theory
- Computation Complexity and Cryptography
- Logic
- Design and Analysis of Algorithms
- Randomness, Geometry, and Discrete Structures
- Theory and Algorithms for Application Domains
- Semantics and Reasoning

Mathematics of Computing

- Discrete Mathematics
- Probability and Statistics
- Mathematical Software
- Information Theory
- Mathematical Analysis
- Continuous Mathematics

Information Systems

- Data Management Systems
- Information Storage Systems
- Information Systems Applications
- World Wide Web

- Information Retrieval

Security and Privacy

- Cryptography
- Formal Methods and Theory of Security
- Security Services
- Intrusion/Anomaly Detection and Malware Mitigation
- Security in Hardware
- Systems Security
- Network Security
- Database and Storage Security
- Software and Application Security
- Human and Societal Aspects of Security and Privacy

Human-Centred Computing

- Human Computer Interaction (HCI)
- Interaction Design
- Collaborative and Social Computing
- Ubiquitous and Mobile Computing
- Visualization
- Accessibility

Computing Methodologies

- Symbolic and Algebraic Manipulation
- Paralled Computing Methodologies
- Artificial Intelligence
- Machine Learning
- Modeling and Simulation
- Computer Graphics
- Distributed Computing Methodologies
- Concurrent Computing Methodologies

Network

- Network Algorithms
- Network Services

Applied Computing

- Electronic Commerce
- Enterprise Computing
- Physical Sciences and Engineering
- Life and Medical Sciences
- Law, Social, and Behavioral Sciences
- Computer Forensics
- Arts and Humanities
- Computers in other Domains
- Operations Research
- Education
- Document Management and Text Processing

3 The Analyzed Projects

In order to obtain a first representative sample of projects to be assessed in this Technology Radar, we collected projects funded in 5 calls across the EU's major recent research and innovation programmes, i.e., FP7 and H2020, that address cybersecurity in their DoAs. These calls are, in alphabetical order:

 H2020-BG-2018-2020

 H2020-ICT-2018-20

 H2020-SC1-FA-DTS-2018-2020

 H2020-SC6-GOVERNANCE-2018-2019-2020

 H2020-SU-ICT-2018-2020

The process of selecting and filtering EC funded projects was a three-step process:

1. Collection of key project data, such as start and end date, budget, call, project type (Research & Innovation Action, Innovation Action, Coordination & Support Action, etc.) coordinator, and high-level project descriptions.
2. Assessment of whether each project in fact does address aspects of digital infrastructure, software technologies, and cybersecurity directly or merely acts as a consumer of outputs of cybersecurity tools and knowledge.
3. Grouped projects according to the Swforum.eu taxonomy domains in primary and secondary classifications.

Once this final list of 51 projects was determined, we applied the methodology described above, arriving at the results provided in section 4 below.

4 The June 2023 Technology Radar

We now present the results of the Radar analysis, initially by sector and then finally bringing them all together to also see the shape of the overall landscape.

4.1 Results by Sector

Below are the results for the projects in each segment of the radar.

4.1.1 Tools & Techniques

Table 1. “Tools and Techniques” Overview

# Projects	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
13	0	0	4	8	1

Tools & Techniques is the most populated primary as well as secondary sector in the radar. This is intuitive as it is part of developing new technological solutions, protecting resources, and helping in the overall software development process.

This includes several projects that are about to finish (Adopt) and/or have already finished and deployed (Hold). In some cases, the technologies implemented are likely to have been superseded by outputs from more latterly funded activities.

Figure 6. “Tools and Techniques” radar segment

Table 2. “Tools and Techniques” projects details

Project name	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-
AMPERE	Jan 2020	Dec 2022				X	
ARTICONF	Jan 2019	Dec 2021				X	
FogProtect	Jan 2020	Dec 2022				X	
MORPHEMIC	Jan 2020	Dec 2022				X	
CPSoSaware	Jan 2020	Dec 2022				X	

Project name	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-
HUB4CLOUD	Jan 2021	Jun 2022				X	
INFINITECH	Oct 2019	Dec 2022				X	
DEEPHEALTH	Jan 2019	Jun 2022				X	
VeriDevOps	Oct 2020	Sept 2023			X		
IoT-NGIN	Oct 2020	Sept 2023			X		
TERMINET	Nov 2020	Nov 2023			X		
ADMORPH	Jan 2020	Dec 2022			X		
MOZILLA	-	-					X

4.1.2 Tools & Techniques and Languages & Frameworks

Table 3. “Tools & Techniques and Languages & Frameworks” Overview

# Projects	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
9	0	0	3	3	3

This sector is the second most populated segment of the radar with the primary classification still being Tools & Techniques. These projects are mostly in their Trial phase with a few that are ready to be adopted. Although their primary focus is still tools and techniques, they are also focusing on some aspects of implementing a new framework or a programming language to achieve their goals.

Figure 7. “Tools & Techniques and Languages & Frameworks” radar segment

Table 4. “Tools & Techniques and Languages & Frameworks” projects details

Project name	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
PIACERE	Dec 2020	Nov 2023			X		
ASSIST-IoT	Nov 2020	Oct 2023			X		
COSMOS	Jan 2021	Dec 2023			X		
PolicyCloud	Jan 2020	Dec 2022				X	
IoTWINS	Sept 2019	Aug 2022				X	
UP2DATE	Jan 2020	Dec 2022				X	
.NET	-	-					X
OPENJS	-	-					X
OPENSTREET	-	-					X

4.1.3 Platforms and Tools & Techniques

Table 5. “Platforms and Tools & Techniques” overview

# Projects	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
6	0	0	1	3	2

This area also holds a significant number of projects with majority of the projects in Adopt or Hold stages. This is one of the few areas where the projects are ripe now and in the stages of ready to be deployed or already been deployed. The majority of the projects in this area provide a platform to build a software upon, but also give users a particular tool/technique to aid in the development process.

Figure 8. “Platforms and Tools & Techniques” radar segment

Table 6. “Platforms and Tools & Techniques” projects details

Project name	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
RAINBOW	Jan 2020	Dec 2022				X	
ADEPTNESS	Jan 2020	Dec 2022				X	
TEACHING	Jan 2020	Dec 2022			X		
BlueCloud	Oct 2019	Sept 2022				X	
ECLIPSE	-	-					X
WordPress	-	-					X

4.1.4 Languages & Frameworks

Table 7. “Languages & Frameworks” overview

# Projects	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
9	0	0	5	1	3

This sector holds projects that are only focused on developing a programming language/framework without any secondary classification. Most of the projects in this segment are still in the earlier stages of development and are at least 18 months away from completion.

Figure 9. “Languages & Frameworks” radar segment

Table 8. “Languages & Frameworks” projects details

Project name	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
1-SWARM	Jan 2020	Dec 2022				X	

Project name	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
XANDAR	Jan 2021	Dec 2023			X		
CHARITY	Jan 2021	Dec 2023			X		
AI-SPRINT	Jan 2021	Dec 2023			X		
IntelloT	Oct 2020	Sept 2023			X		
ELEGANT	Jan 2021	Dec 2023			X		
Python	-	-					X
F#	-	-					X
Perl	-	-					X

4.1.5 Languages & Frameworks and Tools & Techniques

Table 9. “Languages & Frameworks and Tools & Techniques” overview

# Projects	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
6	0	0	3	1	2

There are a small number of projects focusing on Languages & Frameworks to provide users with the ability to code more efficiently while also incorporating other methods to aid the process of the software development process. These can be more generic types of tools or can be high level frameworks. Most projects in this category are still in the early phases of their development cycle, while a couple are ready to be adopted.

Figure 10. “Languages & Frameworks and Tools & Techniques” radar segment

Table 10. “Languages & Frameworks and Tools & Techniques” projects details

Project name	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
FOCETA	Oct 2020	Sept 2023			X		
MEDINA	Nov 2020	Nov 2023			X		
ACCORDION	Jan 2020	Dec 2022				X	
FISHY	Sept 2020	Aug 2023			X		
Apache	-	-					X
TeX	-	-					X

4.1.6 Tools & Techniques and Platforms

Table 11. “Tools & Techniques and Platforms” overview

# Projects	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
8	0	0	3	3	2

A few projects are focusing on developing a tool/technique to aid the software development by providing the users with a platform, such as JVM, virtual platforms, etc. Most of the projects are still in the early phases of their life cycle and will take over a year before they are ready to be tested and deployed.

Figure 11. “Tools & Techniques and Platforms” radar segment

Table 12. “Tools & Techniques and Platforms” projects details

Project	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-
PLEDGER	Dec 2019	Dec 2022				X	
IoTAC	Sept 2020	Aug 2023			X		
SERRANO	Jan 2021	Dec 2023			X		
Ingenious	Oct 2020	Mar 2023				X	
PHYSICS	Jan 2021	Dec 2023			X		
FASTEN	Jan 2019	Jun 2022				X	
Wikimedia	-	-					X
GraphQL	-	-					X

4.1.7 Platforms

Table 13. “Platforms” overview

# Projects	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
4	0	0	1	1	2

This sector contains projects that are solely focused on developing a platform, such as JVM, hybrid clouds, or virtual platforms on which users are able to build software. These projects are still in the very early stages of their life cycle (Trial and Adopt) and will take at least 12 months before they are ready to be beta-tested and deployed.

Figure 12. “Platforms” radar segment

Table 14. “Platforms” projects details

Project name	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
SELENE	Dec 2019	Nov 2022				X	
VEDLIoT	Nov 2020	Oct 2023			X		
PostgreSQL	-	-					X
Linux	-	-					X

4.1.8 Platforms and Languages & Frameworks

Table 15. "Platforms and Languages & Frameworks" overview

# Projects	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
1	0	0	1	0	0

This is one of the least populated sectors of the radar. Rightly so, there are not a lot of projects that focus on developing a platform while also providing a framework for users to build something with. There is one project in this that has already been finished while the other is in the very early stages of its development.

Figure 13. "Platforms and Languages & Frameworks" radar segment

Table 16. "Platforms and Languages & Frameworks" projects details

Project name	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
DataCloud	Jan 2021	Dec 2023			X		

4.1.9 Languages & Frameworks and Platforms

Table 17. “Languages & Frameworks and Platforms” overview

# Projects	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
2	0	0	0	0	2

This is the least populated segment of the radar with only project that was completed in June 2021. This is quite intuitive as developing a framework while also giving users a platform to develop on is not something very commonplace.

Figure 14. “Languages & Frameworks and Platforms” radar segment

Table 18. “Languages & Frameworks and Platforms” projects details

Project name	Start Date	End date	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source
Mambo	-	-					X
Django	-	-					X

4.2 Segments Overview

Table 19. “March 2022 SWForum Technology Radar” overview

Segment	Assess	Trial	Adopt	Hold	Open-Source	Total
Tools & Techniques	0	0	4	8	1	13

Tools & Techniques and Languages & Frameworks	0	0	3	3	3	9
Tools & Techniques and Platforms	0	0	3	3	2	8
Platforms	0	0	1	1	2	4
Platforms and Tools & Techniques	0	0	1	3	2	6
Platforms and Languages & Frameworks	0	0	1	0	0	1
Languages & Frameworks	0	0	5	1	3	9
Languages & Frameworks and Platforms	0	0	0	0	2	2
Languages & Frameworks and Tools & Techniques	0	0	3	1	2	6
	0	0	21	20	17	58

Figure 15. June 2023 SWForum Technology Radar, showing 51 analyzed SWForum.eu projects and 17 open-source projects distributed radially into bands based on their maturity level.

5 Conclusions

The projects are all collected from the SWForum Hub owned and managed by Trust-IT services. All the projects in this radar have been classified into segments by members of SWForum.eu based on feedback received from the projects as well as the project descriptions on their respective webpages. The projects are placed into a ring automatically based on its expiry date. The taxonomy filters are applied based on a combination of the descriptions obtained from the project's website, general interactions from the projects through collecting MTRL assessments, and their MTRL assessment forms.

A number of projects have expired more than 12 months ago due to which they were automatically removed from the radar. The current status of the radar shows that projects are well underway to finish their deliverables and be rolled out into the market or are already doing so. There haven't been any new additions to the SWForum hub as there are no new calls and hence projects that SWForum.eu is being asked to support, and to the radar as a result, since the last deliverable D2.6

The colour of the blips show projects that have been assigned an MTRL score have coloured edges based on the score as described in D2.5 [1], while the projects without a score have black edges. This colouring allows to compare how projects are performing relative to other projects in the same segment.

The analysis of the 51 projects from relevant calls is very important in the broader scope of the SWForum.eu project and, particularly, introducing project results and services into the SME end-user club and marketplace. This radar can help projects track their progress and be prepared to roll out their product into the market.

6 References

- [1] D. Wallom and R. Agrawal, “D2.6 Project Radar Taxonomies,” 2022.
- [2] R. Agrawal and D. Wallom, “Project Radar Landscape Analysis v1,” 2022.
- [3] ThoughtWorks, “ThoughtWorks Technology Radar,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.thoughtworks.com/radar>.
- [4] R. Agrawal and D. Wallom, “MTRL Methodology and Assessment D4.5,” 2023.

DRAFT

Appendix: EC-funded Projects reference

The following projects were included and analysed in this deliverable, in alphabetical order.

Table 20. List of projects funded by EC under the broad categories of SWForum.eu

Project	Call	Type	Start	End
1-SWARM	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
ACCORDION	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
ADEPTNESS	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
ADMORPH	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
AI-SPRINT	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2021	Dec 2023
AMPERE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
ARTICONF	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2019	Dec 2021
ASCLEPIOS	H2020-SC1-FA-DTS-2018-2020	RIA	Dec 2018	Mar 2022
ASSIST-IoT	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Nov 2020	Oct 2023
Blue Cloud	H2020-BG-2018-2020	IA	Oct 2019	Sept 2022
CHARITY	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2021	Dec 2023
COSMOS	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2021	Dec 2023
CPSoSaware	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
CYBELE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	IA	Jan 2019	Dec 2021
DataCloud	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2021	Dec 2023
DECODER	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2019	Dec 2021
DEEPHEALTH	H2020-ICT-2018-20	IA	Jan 2019	Dec 2021
ELEGANT	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2021	Dec 2023
EVOLVE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	IA	Dec 2018	Nov 2021
FASTEN	H2020-ICT-2018-20	IA	Jan 2019	Dec 2021
FISHY	H2020-SU-ICT-2018-2020	RIA	Sept 2020	Aug 2023
FOCETA	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Oct 2020	Sept 2023
FogProtect	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
HUB4CLOUD	H2020-ICT-2018-20	CSA	Jan 2021	Jun 2022
INFINITECH	H2020-ICT-2018-20	IA	Oct 2019	Dec 2022
Ingenious	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Oct 2020	Mar 2023
IntelloT	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Oct 2020	Sept 2023
IoTAC	H2020-SU-ICT-2018-2020	RIA	Sept 2020	Aug 2023
IoT-NGIN	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Oct 2020	Sept 2023

Project	Call	Type	Start	End
IoTWINS	H2020-ICT-2018-20	IA	Sept 2019	Aug 2022
LEXIS	H2020-ICT-2018-20	IA	Jan 2019	Dec 2021
MEDINA	H2020-SU-ICT-2018-2020	RIA	Nov 2020	Nov 2023
MORPHEMIC	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
ONTOCHAIN	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Sept 2020	Aug 2023
PHSYICS	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2021	Dec 2023
PIACERE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Dec 2020	Nov 2023
PLEDGER	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Dec 2019	Nov 2022
PolicyCLOUD	H2020-SC6-GOVERNANCE-2018-2019-2020	IA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
RADON	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2019	June 2021
RAINBOW	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
ReachOut	H2020-ICT-2018-20	CSA	Jan 2019	Dec 2021
SELENE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Dec 2019	Nov 2022
SERRANO	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2021	Dec 2023
SODALITE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Feb 2019	Jan 2022
TEACHING	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
TERMINET	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Nov 2020	Nov 2023
UNICORE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	IA	Jan 2019	Dec 2021
UP2DATE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2020	Dec 2022
VEDLIoT	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Nov 2020	Oct 2023
VeriDevOps	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Oct 2020	Sept 2023
XANDAR	H2020-ICT-2018-20	RIA	Jan 2021	Dec 2023